

IRRATIONAL INEQUALITIES

Yuldoshev Mansur Najmiddin ugli

mansuryuldoshev212901@mail.ru

Academic Lyceum of Tashkent State University of

Economics lead math science teacher

student of master's degree of UzMu

Abstract. In this article, irrational inequalities, which are one of the mathematical properties, are described in detail and examples are written.

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The influence of the didactical contract on the students is remarkable: in this paper, we shall examine a “chapter” of the mathematical education in the High School (in particular, pupils aged 16-17 years) and we shall expose some considerations about its learning [Brousseau, 1987]. Irrational inequalities are often introduced (for example in the II class or in the III class of the Italian Liceo scientifico) particularly referring to the irrational inequalities of 2nd degree. Their resolution is based upon rules, given by the teacher and often learnt by heart by the students; but not always, as we shall see, their application is critical. The resolution of an irrational inequality is a very common exercise, in the standard mathematical curriculum of the High School. The following rules are well-known:

$$\sqrt{A(x)} \leq B(x) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \begin{cases} A(x) \geq 0 \\ B(x) \geq 0 \\ A(x) \leq [B(x)]^2 \end{cases}$$

$$\sqrt{A(x)} \geq B(x) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \begin{cases} A(x) \geq 0 \\ B(x) \leq 0 \end{cases} \vee \begin{cases} B(x) \geq 0 \\ A(x) \geq [B(x)]^2 \end{cases}$$

The resolution of any irrational quadratic inequality is often based upon the (critical or mechanical?) application of these rules. First of all, let us underline that this application is not always strictly necessary; let us consider, for example, the inequality:

$$\sqrt{x} + 2 \leq 0$$

It is verified by no $x \in \mathbf{R}$: but it is *not* necessary to use the rules to obtain this result. Their use brings to the following (correct) resolution:

$$\sqrt{x} + 2 \leq 0 \Rightarrow \sqrt{x} \leq -2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x \geq 0 \\ -2 \geq 0 \\ x \leq (-2)^2 \end{cases}$$

For students weak in Math, there is no need to be disheartened about the seemingly high mathematical content. I would advise you to go through this chapter and internalise the concepts. However, keep in mind the fact that in an aptitude test, the questions will have options, and with options all you will need to do will be check the validity of the inequality for the different options. In fact, the questions in this chapter have options on both the levels and with option-based solutions, all these questions will seem easy to you. However, I would advise students aiming to score high marks in Quantitative Ability to try to mathematically solve all the questions on all three levels in this chapter (even though option-based solution will be much easier.) Two real numbers or two algebraic expressions related by the symbol $>$ (“Greater Than”) or $<$ (“Less Than”) (and also by the signs \geq or \leq) form an inequality. $A < B$, $A > B$ (are plain inequalities) $A \geq B$, $A \leq B$ (are called as inequations) The inequality consists of two sides—the left hand side, A and the right hand side, B. A and B can be algebraic expressions or they can be numbers. An inequality with the $<$ or $>$ sign is called a strict inequality while an inequality having \geq or \leq sign is called a slack inequality. The expressions A and B have to be considered on the set where A and B have sense simultaneously. This set is called the set of permissible values of the inequality. If the terms on the LHS and the RHS are algebraic equations/identities,

then the inequality may or may not hold true for a particular value of the variable/set of variables assumed.

Let there be n factors a, b, c, \dots, n , of a composite number and suppose that their sum is constant and equal to S . Consider the product $abc \dots n$, and suppose that a and b are any two unequal factors. If we replace the two unequal factors a and b by the two equal factors $(a + b)/2$, and $(a + b)/2$, the product is increased while the sum remains unaltered. Hence, so long as the product contains two unequal factors it can be increased altering the sum of the factors; therefore, the product is greatest when all the factors are equal. In this case the value of each of the n factors is S/n , and the greatest value of the product is $(S/n)^n$, or $\{(a + b + c + \dots + n/n)^n$. This will be clearer through an example. Let us define a number as $a \times b = c$ such that we restrict $a + b = 100$ (maximum). Then, the maximum value of the product will be achieved if we take the value of a and b as 50 each. Thus $50 \times 50 = 2500$ will be the highest number achieved for the restriction $a + b \leq 100$. Further, you can also say that $50 \times 50 > 51 \times 49 > 52 \times 48 > 53 \times 47 > 54 \times 46 > \dots > 98 \times 2 > 99 \times 1$. Thus if we have a larger multiplication as $4 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8$ this will always be less than $5 \times 5 \times 7 \times 8$. [Holds true only for positive numbers.]

Let there be given several inequalities in one unknown. If it is required to find the number that will be the solution of all the given equalities, then the set of these inequalities is called a system of inequalities. The solution of a system of inequalities in one unknown is defined as the value of the unknown for which all the inequalities of the system reduce to true numerical inequalities. To solve a system of inequalities means to find all the solutions of the system or to establish that there is none. Two systems of inequalities are said to be equivalent if any solution of one of them is a solution of the other, and vice versa. If both the systems of inequalities have no solution, then they are also regarded to be equivalent. If the inequality includes functions under the root sign, then such inequalities are called irrational. The standard method for solving these inequalities is to raise both sides of the inequality to the desired power: if the

inequality includes a square root, then square it; the root of the third degree enters - into the cube, etc. However, squaring without violating the equivalence is only possible for an inequality for which both sides are non-negative. When squaring inequalities, parts of which have different signs, inequalities can be obtained that are both equivalent to the original one and not equivalent to it. The main method for solving irrational inequalities is the method of reducing the original inequality to an equivalent system or to a set of systems of rational inequalities. The solution of an inequality is the set of values of a variable for which the given inequality becomes a true numerical inequality. Two inequalities are said to be equivalent if their solution sets are the same.

When solving irrational inequalities, as a rule, it is necessary to raise both parts of the inequality to natural powers. Such transformations can lead to inequalities that are not equivalent to the original one, and since the set of solutions in most cases is an infinite set, it is impossible to test the resulting solutions by substitution. The only way that guarantees the correct answer is to apply exclusively equivalent transformations of inequalities. In this regard, we present the corresponding statements, which are often used in solving irrational inequalities (in all statements, n is a natural number).

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